

Webinar – European Standardisation Panel Survey

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The role of standardisation in knowledge valorisation

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Why Integrate Standards, Research & Innovation

Bridge the Innovation Gap for Impact at Global Scale

Standards De-risk & Accelerate Technology-Product-Service Development, Adoption & Scaling

Political Agenda

The European Green Deal

A European Industrial Strategy

Advanced Materials Communication

Standardisation Strategy

Chips Act

COM Recommendation on critical technology areas

BE PRES Council Conclusions on Knowledge Valorisation

Valorisation channels

Policy context - ERA Action 7: Outcomes

Guiding principles for knowledge valorisation

- Adopting a common line on policy instruments for improving knowledge sharing and valorisation in Europe.
- Introducing broad approach by addressing intellectual assets management, linkage to standardisation and policy-making, industry-academia collaborations and involvement of citizens.

Council Recommendation adopted on 2 December 2022

The Guiding principles are **supported** by:

i) Codes of practice on **intellectual assets management** and on **standardisation**

Commission Recommendations adopted on 1 March 2023

ii) Codes of practice on **industry-academia co-creation** and **citizen engagement for knowledge valorisation**

Commission Recommendations adopted on 1 March 2024

Standardisation Strategy – the key actions

No alignment with political priorities

- Enhance Annual WP to reflect standardisation urgencies
- High-Level Forum to assist in prioritisation
- Review of all harmonised European standards against contribution to zero-emission economy and Europe's Digital Decade
- EU excellence hub and Chief Standardisation Officer

Good governance concerns

- Proposal for amendment → introducing good governance principles for ESOs
- Call to ESOs to modernise their governance
- Announce the Evaluation of Regulation 1025/2012
- MS peer review process on SME-friendly conditions

Geopolitics of standards

- Coordination of EU MS/NSB positions
- International standards for a free, open and secure global internet
- EU funding (Horizon, NICI), pilots in African countries and EU Neighbourhood
- Continuation of concerted actions with like-minded partners (TTC, Japan)

Unexploited potential of pre-normative work

- Code of Practice for researchers
- Standardisation Booster

Lack of experts

- Targeted actions on education and skills:
 - Horizon Europe/COST
 - EU Academy Platform/e-learning material
 - Standardisation University Days

Code of practice on standardisation

Based on the lessons learnt and success factors from examples of Horizon 2020 projects

Higher education
institutions and
research & innovation
organisations

Project partners

Policy and
stakeholders

Inclusiveness – all types of projects with a wide range of TRLs

ESPS – how it complements the ongoing initiatives

Understanding the demand for R&I based standardisation by creating a comprehensive database that

- Analyses current activities and future trends in the R&I – standardisation interface
- Serves as an input for standards policy
- Raises the importance of standardisation for businesses

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